

A Study on the Kinetics of Bromination of Cinnamic Acid and its Derivatives (Part I) in Methyl Alcohol as Solvent

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The bimolecular rate constants and energies of activation have been measured for the bromination of cinnamic acid and its mono, di- and tri-substituted derivatives in methyl alcohol. The energy of activation is lowered if the electron releasing groups like methyl, iso-propyl etc. are attached directly to benzene nucleus of cinnamic acid but the groups like chloro increase the activation energy due to their electron withdrawing power from the reaction center. The frequency factor of the reactions has been found to be more or less constant throughout the reaction series. The resultant effect of the substituents on the energy of activation is the sum of their individual effects and the plot of $\log k$ and $\log K$ (K = Basic dissociation constant in water) is linear.

The bromination of cinnamic acid in nonhydroxylic solvents as carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, carbon disulfide has been studied comprehensively by several authors¹⁻⁵. They inferred that the reaction is bimolecular, non-reversible and autocatalytic in nature. Remick⁶ adduced the evidence that during the halogen addition, halogen acts as an electrophilic reagent. Ingold⁷ and Annantakrishnan⁸ established this fact by showing that electron releasing substituents in olefin as methyl and phenyl groups enhanced the addition while electron withdrawing groups retarded the addition. The possibility of nucleophilic addition was envisaged by Ingold and Ingold⁹ in their comprehensive analysis of conditions determining the halogen addition. It was found by few workers^{10,11} that a solution of bromine in methyl alcohol acted analogously to bromine in water. Meinel¹² made it clear that methyl hypobromite existed in the solution and it acts as an active addition reagent for ethylenic linkage. A high yield of bromo-methoxy compound is obtained in methyl alcohol as given by Jackson¹³ and Connant. They found that by the action of bromine on cinnamic acid

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in methyl alcohol, a mixture of α -bromo— β -methoxy and β - β -dibromo cinnamic acid was formed. The methyl hypobromite was found to add to double bond in the side chain of ethylenic linkage.

In the present work the kinetics of bromination of a large number of mono-, di- and tri-substituted derivatives of cinnamic acid has been undertaken in methyl alcohol in order to find out whether or not (a) the frequency factor remains constant throughout the reaction series, (b) the resultant effect on the activation energy of the substituents in the same benzene nucleus of cinnamic acid is approximately the sum of their individual effects, (c) there is any functional relationship between the reactivities and the dissociation constants of mono-substituted derivatives of cinnamic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) Purification and preparation of material

The solvent methyl alcohol (C. P. Grade) was used after purification. Bromine, AnalaR (E. Merck) and cinnamic acid (B.D.H.) were selected for the purpose.

Since none of the cinnamic acid derivatives were available, all of them were prepared from their respective benzaldehydes by malonic acid condensation process. The methods followed for the preparation of 3-Nitro-4-chloro-benzaldehyde and 2-Chloro-5-nitro-benzaldehyde are those of Erdmann¹⁴ and Hodgson and Beard¹⁵ respectively. Their melting points were found to be 78° and 63°. The tri-substituted derivative 2-4-dichloro-5-nitro-benzaldehyde was prepared by the method adopted by Geigy¹⁶ and its melting point was noted to be 72°.

The cinnamic acid derivatives prepared by the malonic acid condensation process from the respective substituted benzaldehydes were recrystallised several times from the appropriate solvents. The sample obtained had the following melting points.

Compound	Melting point°C
1. <i>o</i> -nitro-	240
2. <i>m</i> -nitro-	202
3. <i>o</i> -chloro-	209
4. <i>m</i> -chloro-	164
5. <i>p</i> -chloro-	243
6. <i>m</i> -methoxy-	117
7. 2-4-dichloro-	234
8. 3-4-dichloro-	218
9. 3-nitro-4-chloro-	182
10. 2-chloro-5-nitro-	22
11. 2-3-dimethoxy-	180
12. 2-4-dichloro-5-nitro-	175

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(b) *Experimental procedure*

The bromination of cinnamic acid takes place according to the equation

provided no other complexities arise due to the reaction between bromine and the solvent, its course can be quantitatively followed by estimating the bromine left at different intervals of time.

The solutions of cinnamic acid (*M*/60) and bromine (*M*/120) were prepared for studying the reaction kinetics. 25 ml's of each of the solutions were mixed at a fixed temperature, 5 ml. of reaction mixture was taken out at regular intervals and 5 ml. of 5 % potassium iodide solution added to it, in order to quench the reaction. The solution was titrated immediately against standard sodium thiosulfate solution, using starch as indicator. The rate constants were calculated by using second order rate equation. At six different temperatures ranging from 20–55° the rate constants were determined. The energy of activation was calculated by applying "least square method".

DISCUSSION

It can be easily concluded from the results given in Table-I that the activation energy is lowered, if the electron releasing substituents like methyl, iso-propyl, etc., are attached directly to benzene nucleus, whereas the groups like chloro, nitro etc., increase the activation energy due to their electron withdrawing nature. The decrease in activation energy caused by methoxy group is also in agreement with the investigations made by Hanson and Williams¹⁷.

TABLE 1

The energy of activation and the frequency factor at 35° for the reaction of bromine with cinnamic acid and its derivatives

Sl. No.	Compound	$k_{35} \times 10^3$ $\rho./\text{mols}/\text{sec.}$	<i>E</i> Cals./gm.mols	log <i>Z</i>
1.	cinnamic acid	21.540	9290	4.87
2.	<i>o</i> -chloro-	5.467	10600	5.26
3.	<i>m</i> -chloro-	3.492	9750	4.46
4.	<i>p</i> -chloro-	11.420	10300	5.35
5.	<i>o</i> -nitro-	4.592	9960	4.73
6.	<i>m</i> -nitro-	3.210	9930	4.55
7.	<i>m</i> -methoxy-	134.300	8700	5.30
8.	<i>p</i> -methyl-	338.600	8430	5.37
9.	<i>p</i> -iso-propyl-	198.400	8000	4.98
10.	2-4-dichloro-	7.058	10700	5.26
11.	3-4-dichloro-	2.801	10200	4.68
12.	2-chloro, 5-nitro-	2.060	11400	5.23
13.	4-chloro, 3-nitro-	2.833	10200	4.53
14.	2-3-dimethoxy-	215.500	7900	4.94
15.	2-4-dichloro, 5-nitro-	2.1144	11600	5.36

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Constancy of frequency factor : It is further observed from Table-1 that the logarithm of frequency factor ($\log A$) is more or less constant for the whole series. This is supported by the fact that the values of $\log k_{35}$ when plotted with the experimental values of activation energies for different derivatives of cinnamic acid, gives a straight line with a slope of $-2.303 RT$ (Fig. 1). So it can be concluded from these results that the changes in velocity

constants at a given temperature caused by different substituents in the benzene ring of cinnamic acid are due to changes in energy of activation only. In some cases, it can be seen from Fig. (1), the points do not fall on the line of slope $-2.303 RT$. For such compounds the velocity constant in the reaction is governed by the changes in frequency factor as well as in the energy of activation. The compounds, which fall on the line of slope $-2.303 RT$, have a frequency factor 9.6×10^4 gm. mols. lit⁻¹ sec⁻¹ and for other compounds it varied from 3×10^4 to 2.3×10^5 gm mols. lit⁻¹ secs⁻¹. According to collision theory the collision number

$$Z = N^2 \sigma 8\pi RT(1/MA + 1/MB)^{\frac{1}{2}} C_A C_B \quad \dots (i)$$

where N is Avogadro's number, σ is the sum of collision radii of reactants, M_A and M_B are the molecular weights of reactants and C_A and C_B the concentration of gm. mols./ml. of A and B respectively since C_A and C_B are the same for the reactions studied, therefore

$$Z = \text{constant} \times \sigma(1/MA + 1/MB)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (ii)$$

It is evident from the the equation (ii) that Z decreases with the increase in molecular weight of the reactants. As bromine is one of the common reactants and the molecular weights of cinnamic acid derivatives vary only slightly from one compound to the other, therefore a constant value of Z is obtained and consequently $\log A$ is constant for the series. The slight variation in frequency factor may be due to different degrees of solvation of cinnamic acid derivatives which have different dipole moments. The bromine will not have any effect, as it is a common reactant throughout the series.

The relationship between velocity constant and dissociation constant of cinnamic acid derivatives: The values of logarithm of dissociating constants ($\log k$) has been plotted against the values of $\log k_{35}$ for different substituted cinnamic acids. The values of dissociation constants in water given by Dippy¹⁸ were used. The plot is found to be a straight line (Fig. 2). This can be explained on the basis of the fact that the dissociating power and the rate of reaction between bromine and cinnamic acid are closely related.

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